

Results of northern blotting of RNA extracted from HSA-LR mice and WT control animals

U6

miR-27

miR-23

miR-24

miR-206

miR-1

miR-133

Pri-miRNAs of miR-23b, miR-27b and miR-24-1 identified in HeLa cells

5' RACE

Pri-miRNAs of miR-23b, miR-27b and miR-24-1 are alternatively spliced and are sensitive to MBNL levels in HeLa

Pri-miRNAs of miR-23b, miR-27b and miR-24-1 identified in mouse cells

pri-miRNA

MBNL1 protein knock-out confirmation

AS events regulated by MBNLs during development

RIP enrichment analysis was performed using an MBNL1-specific antibody on the WT or Mbnl1&2KO (1&2KO) MEFs

RIP-MBNL MEF WT vs1&2KO

RIP-MBNL MEF WT vs1&2KO

